

Relation Between The Square Well Potential and 1-D Reflection-Refraction

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Quantum mechanics is required to solve for reflection and refraction probabilities relative to an incident flux in the one dimensional reflection problem which applies to both photons and particles with rest mass. Historically (1), this problem is solved using the periodic electric field of the photon, which some might argue is not a quantum mechanical solution, but here we try to demonstrate the connection between 1-D reflection-refraction and the quantum square well potential problem, which is usually solved using the time-independent Schrodinger equation and the boundary condition of the wavefunction vanishing at $x=\pm\infty$. We suggest that even though this is the case, the wavefunction outside the well is still an eigenfunction of the translational operator d/dx and argue that this is linked to the nature of escaped particles.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

One dimensional reflection-refraction is a physical problem present in the classical world (e.g photons moving from air to water or from air to glass etc). We argue that this problem requires quantum mechanics to determine the probabilities for a photon to reflect or refract. Traditionally (1), the probabilities, in the photon case, are obtained using the periodic nature of the photon electric field, $E \cos(-\omega t+kx)$ and creating a continuity equation at the n_1-n_2 junction (n =index of refraction) as well as a continuity equation for the first derivative. Thus, some may argue that this is not a quantum mechanical approach, although we note that $E+iB$ (E =electric field vector and B =magnetic field vector) is sometimes (2) taken to be the quantum wavefunction of the photon.) Furthermore, one may solve the problem of one dimensional reflection-refraction for a particle with rest mass using two regions with different constant potential V_1, V_2 , with an interface at $x=0$ and constant particle energy in both. This appears to be a quantum problem for the rest mass particle.

The two continuity equations for this problem are:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ ((1a)) and}$$

$$A p \exp(ipx) - B p \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ ((1b))}$$

Solving ((1a)) and ((1b)) yields:

$$B/A = (p-p_2) / (p+p_2) \text{ ((2a)) and } C/A = 2p_2 / (p+p_2) \text{ ((2b))}$$

The probability to reflect for a photon is: B^2/c and to refract, C^2/c^2 .

Square Well Potential Problem

The quantum square well potential is solved using the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$-\hbar^2/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V W = E W \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{Here } V=-V_0 \text{ for } -L/2 \geq x \leq L/2 \quad ((4a))$$

$$\text{A boundary condition of } W(x=-\infty) = W(x=\infty) = 0. \quad ((4b))$$

The time-independent Schrodinger equation is based on average energy conservation, but also on the notion of spatial invariance for individual p values, i.e.

$$-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

Classically, a particle exists only within the classical turning points, i.e. within ((4a)). If the particle is outside this region, it would be considered to be free, i.e. unbound. An unbound particle has momentum p and nonrelativistic kinetic energy $pp/2m$ and is associated with spatial invariance.

The mathematical solution of W outside of ((4a)), however, is $\exp(kx)$ for $x < -L/2$ and $\exp(-kx)$ for $x > L/2$, where: $k = \sqrt{(2m)(E-V)}$. Now, $E < 0$ and $V < 0$ so $E-V$ is a positive number and the negative E shows how tightly bound the particle is in the ((4a)) region.

We suggest that it is interesting that $\exp(kx)$ and $\exp(-kx)$ are both eigenfunctions of the translational operator d/dx . We suggest that this is linked to the physical notion that an escaped particle exhibits translational invariance. We also note that both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are part of the solution of $\exp(kx)$ and $\exp(-kx)$ if one writes these as $\sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Thus, this is not simply a scenario of escaped particles, but of free incident particles as well.

This, we suggest, implies a reflection-refraction kind of problem, but it is not the same as the usual photon or rest mass particle reflection-refraction in which A and B values have different magnitudes as seen from ((2a)).

The Association Between the Quantum Square Well Potential and One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

Instead of solving the square-well potential problem using the time-independent Schrodinger equation, we consider solving it using one-dimensional reflection-refraction. The problem with this approach, however, is that the solutions ((2a)) and ((2b)) are based on a given A value, with AA being the incident flux. A bound problem should focus on a spatially localized particle and not on incident flux entering the bound region. Furthermore, classically one would not have particles outside the bound region and quantum mechanically the probability is very low for a particle to escape.

We thus propose that in order to treat the square well bound problem in terms of one dimensional reflection-refraction, one should force A and B to have the same value (so to speak), i.e to have the same incident and reflected intensities. Furthermore, in a quantum bound problem one should consider an average momentum. ((2a)) does not allow for $B/A=1$. There is, however, an approach one may use, it seems. One may consider p_2 as a real-valued momentum inside the well and introduce a purely imaginary momentum outside, i.e, p. In such a

case, B/A is the ratio of two complex numbers with the same modulus. This then allows one to solve the problem because ((1a)) and ((1b)) then become the continuity equations which would apply in the time-independent Schrodinger equation case.

It is interesting to note that here one does not need solutions of the Schrodinger equation, because one has translational invariance in both the bound region and the outside-the-well regions which should be manifest mathematically. We argue that this manifestation is through:

$$d/dx W = \text{constant } W \quad ((6))$$

We noted already that in order to use the one dimensional reflection-refraction approach one requires a purely imaginary momentum outside the well. This suggests a negative energy outside the well because $V=0$ in this region. How may one describe a negative energy when free particles have positive energy? The idea of a negative energy makes sense within the bound region because it may describe how tightly bound a particle is.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the quantum square-well potential problem is usually solved using the time-independent Schrodinger equation and the boundary condition $W(x=\infty)=W(x=-\infty)=0$. The fact that the solutions inside the well $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ and outside (x negative) $\exp(kx)$ and (x positive) $\exp(-kx)$ are eigenfunctions of the translational operator d/dx does not seem to be stressed. We ask: Why is this the case? Furthermore, tunneled particles should be free and have positive energy and momentum, not negative energy and a purely complex momentum k .

In order to analyze the square-well potential problem, we try to consider it in terms of one dimensional reflection-refraction. The problem, however, is that such a problem is solved in terms of A , the square root flux of the incident beam. A bound particle in a square well does not have an incident beam whose flux may be adjusted. We thus suggest that a reflected ray is equivalent to an escaped beam which should match the incident beam. In such a case, the incident beam flux is not arbitrary. For this to be the case, $B/A = (p-p^2)/(p+p^2)$ should be 1, but this cannot be for real p values. Furthermore, p^2 , the momentum inside the well should be real so it seems that one must make p purely imaginary to allow for $(p-p^2)$ and $p+p^2$ to have the same modulus. This in turn requires energy outside the well to be negative to create a purely imaginary p . Escaped (reflected) or incident particles, however, have positive energy, so how can one have a negative energy? It is possible if it describes the tightness of the bound state in the well. As a final note, we suggest that the fact that $\exp(kx)$ (x negative) and $\exp(-ikx)$ (x positive) outside the well having translational invariance describes the fact that incident and reflected beams have such invariance. Thus, even though a strictly dropping function $\exp(-kx)/\exp(kx)$ is used, the notion of translational symmetry tied to free particles is still present.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change

2. Białynicki-Birula, I. On the Wavefunction of the Photon *Acta Physica Polonica* Vol 86 (1994)
<http://przyrbwn.icm.edu.pl/APP/PDF/86/a086z1p08.pdf>